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OIKODOMOS

a virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe

WORKPACKAGE PROM

Report on the Grenoble/Bratislava Pilot Studio

Authors: Jan Tucny, Stéphane Sadoux

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This document summarises the actions undertaken as part of the Grenoble-Bratislava Pilot Studio and the ways in which this virtual collaborative work was used as a promotion tool for the OIKODOMOS project.

Activities undertaken included studio work, carried out both synchronously and asynchronously, and at a distance and on site. Contacts were initiated with local authorities and local practitioners in both countries so as to enhance the multi-professional dimension of the project and to promote the project across disciplines.

The project was also presented to the press in Bratislava during the field trip organised within the context of the pilot studio.

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1) General information

As part of the OIKODOMOS project, a pilot studio was organised and run by the schools of architecture from IUG Grenoble and FA STU Bratislava between February and April 2008. The topic of the studio was housing and urban development in Bratislava. Thirty eight students were involved, along with teachers from both universities and a number of practitioners acting as external tutors.

1.1) Date of the event:

January 2008 – May 2008

1.2) Participants:

Students

38 students from IUG Grenoble, 1st year of Master Study, Course of Urban Planning & International Cooperation

15 students from FA STU Bratislava, 3rd year of Bachelor Study, Course of Architecture and Urban Design,

Professors

IUG: Jan Tucny, Jacques Lacoste, Stéphane Sadoux,
FA STU: L'ubica Vítková, Viera Joklova, Igor Koščo

Associated professional tutors:

JJ Faure, Architect, President of French Society of Town Planners SFU-Rhône-Alpes
Ph. Caparros, Charge de mission, New Town Isle d'Abeau

2) Actions undertaken

A number of actions were initiated as part of the Grenoble-Bratislava Pilot Studio. Experimental teaching and learning methods were developed and tested by students, teachers and professionals who were associated to the studio.

2.1) Virtual Design Studio

Student distant studio dealing with housing and development projects for Bratislava were organised and run over a period of three months. Group work brought together students from Grenoble and Bratislava, whose task was to deal with a selection of places in Bratislava or nearby (Inner City-Mlynske Nivy / Satellite towns-Lamacska Brana / Cross-Border Development area Petrzalka-Kitsee-Wolfstahl).

ICT were widely used tools for project design, communication, data exchanges, complementary lectures, coordination of national teams, in line with the OIKODOMOS project objectives.

2.2) Academic and non academic partnership

Collaborative actions were initiated with FA STU Bratislava and City Council of Bratislava for the definition of project outcomes, exchanges of housing development experiences and student work evaluation.

French professionals associated to the design studio in Grenoble and via OIKODOMOS website from Lyon and New Town of Isle d'Abeau acted as tutors.

2.3) Student on-site field trip and design studio in Bratislava

A one week field trip to Bratislava (from 13/05/2008 to 20/05/2008) was organised and run.

Students were offered an opportunity to put their work in perspective on site and to have a closer look at the urban context whilst presenting their projects to the local authority, to the media, to academics and professionals.

2.4) OIKODOMOS project and VDS promotion

Contacts were made with partners and the media. Tools developed for OIKODOMOS were presented, so were student projects through exhibitions.

3) OIKODOMOS Project and VDS promotion

3.1) Symposium Grenoble 7th – 8th of February 2008

The distant workshop was launched in February 2008, with a first inaugural videoconference between FA-STU Bratislava and IUG Grenoble. This session was organised during a research Symposium (IVE Rencontres internationales d'Urbanisme) hosted by the University of Grenoble and the PACTE-Territoire research centre.

The local project team presented the HOUSING@21.EU case study repository and a demo session of the OIKODOMOS website to the audience (200 delegates) and highlighted the main goals of the Virtual Campus. A videoconference with Bratislava initiated the student design studio with a presentation of selected sites, exchanges with Slovak colleagues and local participants. A flyer in French and English was handed out to delegates. The session, recorded on video (40 minutes) is accessible by streaming via Real Player on the UPMF Multimedia EAD-TICE Centre video server at the address <rtsp://elvire.msh-alpes.fr/tice/upmf/iug/oiko1.rm>.

3.2) AESOP Best teaching programme contest

The Association of the European Schools of Planning, AESOP, organises a competition between member schools every year for the prize of Best Teaching Programme. Pilot Virtual Design Studio Grenoble-Bratislava, based on the OIKODOMOS project will be presented for the 2007/2008 academic year.

3.3) Association of professionals

Several contacts and meetings with French regional and national representatives of architects and planners were organised in January and February in Lyon in order to present the OIKODOMOS project and to set out the principles of Virtual Campus. Members of the SFU (Société Française des Urbanistes) and of its executive committee ARU-RAA (Association régionale des Urbanistes Rhône-Alpes et Auvergne) expressed their interest for ICT learning tools as a media and space for short Lifelong Learning modules offered to Architects and Town Planners like a contribution to their continuing professional development schemes.

A specific meeting with representatives of L'Isle d'Abeau Local Council (French New Town located between Lyon and Grenoble) in March allowed the Grenoble team to associate two professionals (senior SFU architect and environmental planner) to the Pilot Design Studio Grenoble-Bratislava. These professionals acted as external tutors and advised students and supervised project group-work.

A national centre for architectural innovation (Grands Ateliers d'Architecture GAA) is located in New Town of Isle d'Abeau. The centre is run by a consortium of French Schools of Architecture, financed by Region Rhône-Alpes, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Territorial Planning and local authorities. Regional contacts with GAA partners may allow us to associate GAA to the next Workshop Grenoble, scheduled in March 2009 as an activity of the OIKODOMOS workpackage PREA2.

3.4) Pilot Virtual Design Studio Bratislava presentation

Four student's teams managed by IUG Grenoble and FA-STU Bratislava experienced a common distant studio activity over a three month period. At the end of this period, French students were offered an opportunity to assess their projects, developed through ICT, in the light of local reality. An on-site workshop took place at FA STU during their field trip in Bratislava. Students from IUG Grenoble presented their designs to Bratislava teachers, students and the representatives of the Mayor's Office, who gave them advice and comments. All these have been used and incorporated to their projects so as to enhance the final designs which were presented at the end of the workshop.

3.5) Media contacts and dissemination

Exhibition in FA-STU

An exhibition located in the main lobby of the School of Architecture FA-STU Bratislava presented the OIKODOMOS project and selected students works from Virtual Design Studio for 2 weeks in May 2008. In June 2008 part of this presentation was shown in SAS (Union of Slovak Architects) palace in Bratislava downtown.

Exhibition in Grenoble

A similar poster and power-point based exhibition took place in Grenoble University – Cité des Territoires building.

Research symposium release

OIKODOMOS project and VDS Bratislava studio were presented to participants on research symposium „Villes et constructeurs, qualité environnementale des bâtiments“ (Cities and builders, environmental quality of housing) organised in 10-11/06/2008 in IUG-Cité des Territoires by MOBAT and French Agency for sustainable environment and energy ADEME.

Website IUG-UPMF

The OIKODOMOS pilot VDS studio „atelier“ overview is presented on the IUG website (www.iug-grenoble.fr) and studio specific workspace site (<http://webtek-02.upmf-grenoble.fr>)

Radio and press release Bratislava

Slovak national radio SR2-Regina broadcasted interviews with French and Slovak students and teachers participating on the OIKODOMOS VDS Bratislava studio. The programme is accessible via SR website

(<http://www.slovakradio.sk/inetportal/2007/index.php?lang=1&stationID=4&page=showNews&id=52000&searchText=Tatiana+Linetov%C3%A1>).

Due to local contacts established by our colleagues from Slovak OIKODOMOS team, Slovak professional review Informacie-Architektura-Design

(<http://www.wwwstranky.sk/yudiny/main.php?p=informacie>) will publish interviews and presentation of VDS and OIKODOMOS programme in its June-July 2008 issue.